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ARON E. MORALES, LPT, MAEd

Faculty

Research Instructor, College of Management

Northwest Samar State University

Samar, Region VIII, Philippines

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Silent Screams of the Innocent

In the deepest wild in the forsaken land,
A caged bird ready to be free and become wild.
Its blood and strength soaked-wasted in the native hands,
In the eyes of saint-like, ungrateful, unprincipled termites.

A bird whose set to soar high and claim its freedom,
but chained by the ambitions of the flesh-eating parasites.
The bird is willing to speak but a fist of colony in his mouth,
threats of the unethical and unbothered devil-alike.

Insect's fangs so thick, sharp, and hard,
It never misses to penetrate and killed its prey on the spot.
Spit of venom from its foul, carnivorous mouth,
Can snatch, still, the life from the flock of birds; death will take its part.

False and turmoil stories is what they prophesized
They send these creatures as decoy in the quick sand,
as these winged-animals try to flap and move their feet on the ground,
It's life being drag in the pit of death and beyond.

Now they pin their blames to all innocent ones,
put the weight in the shoulders of the unapologetic one,
so heavy it may cause and take a life.
Is this how the birds are paid for the labor they had?

These flock are tired in flapping their wings so hard,
the dreams to be free and feel the breeze of the sky,
a vision of peace, freedom, and array of clouds
Birds who hope for a sweet tomorrow when sunrise flourish in the sky.